

To Investigate Thermal and Mechanical Properties of Binary Epoxy Nanocomposites

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Abstract:

Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (DDS) intercalated magnesium aluminium layered double hydroxide (Mg Al SDS LDHs) were synthesized and used as additives for the preparation of epoxy nanocomposites. The properties of the additives and their epoxy nano-composites were characterized by X-ray diffractometer (XRD), SEM, UTM and TGA. The Mg-Al SDS LDH additions into the epoxy resin, which was shown by a stable improvement of the thermal properties of the nanocomposites as to comparison to virgin epoxy resin. Due to the presence of Mg-Al SDS LDH, the epoxy nano-composites developed a rigid and dense upper layer, with stable charring, which prevented the escape of the decomposed flammable volatiles and protected the lower layer of the nanocomposites from further decomposition. The mechanical strength of these composites was also assessed. The strength of the composites was found to increase linearly on increasing the Mg Al SDS LDHs content. An enhancement in the properties was observed after toughening the epoxy resin.

Key words: Sodium Dodecyl sulphate, X-ray diffractometer, Thermal and Mechanical Properties

I. Introduction

Epoxy matrix are one of the most vital types of thermosetting polymers resin and have extensively use as structural materials, structural adhesives, and matrix resins for fiber reinforced nanocomposites. They are easily breakable and have poor resistance to crack

propagation. The toughness of bi-functional epoxy matrix such as DGEBA has been increased by blending with many type materials [1-4].

The investigated showed that the addition of nano fillers into the epoxy matrix can significantly progress the mechanical and thermal properties [5-6]. The reinforcement of epoxy polymer matrix by the inorganic nanofillers such as Titanium dioxide (TiO_2), Zinc Oxide (ZnO), nano-clay, carbon nano-tubes, Carbon blacks and Calcium Carbonate (CaCO_3) were attracted to many research scholar and scientists. The addition of nano fillers (particle size less than 100 nm) into the epoxy polymer matrix affects very much to the properties of nano-composites due to their larger surface area and the homogeneous dispersion within the macro molecules up to certain extent [7-8]. However, one of the basic problems associated with the nanofillers is the tendency to agglomerate during the mixing with the polymer resin matrix [9]. This shortfall can be bridged by prolong mechanical mixing and followed by ultra sonication of the nanofiller/resin mixture [10].

Various literature survey focused on epoxy nanocomposites such as Ng et al.[11] developed epoxy nano-composites containing TiO_2 and result shows that the toughness of the nanocomposites is better than that traditional material filled epoxy composites. Wetzel et al.[12] introduced two nanofiller like CaSiO_3 and Al_2O_3 into epoxy resin matrix. They found nanoparticles can deviate and branch the crack front or even pin it, forcing a higher energy absorption in the composite when crack occurred. Chen *et al.* [13] reported the effect of CaCO_3 concentration on the mechanical properties of blocked polyurethane/epoxy interpenetrating polymer networks and they reported that mechanical properties like tensile strength, flexural strength, tensile modulus, and flexural modulus of IPNs improved with CaCO_3 concentration to a utmost value at 5, 10, 20, and 25 phr, respectively. Wang *et al.* [14] developed epoxy resin/ CaCO_3 composites by the methods of extruding, solution, blending, as well as *in situ* and inclusion polymerization

In this paper study, the nanocomposites were prepared by mechanical mixing of epoxy resins and Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate. The effect of nano size of filler on the mechanical properties viz., tensile strength, elongation-at-break, impact strength and hardness was studied.

II. Experimental

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419

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2.1 Materials

Epoxy resin was commercially available and was used without any further purification (Pliogrip resin and Chemicals Pvt. Ltd, Dombivali, Mumbai, (India)). Grade PG-100; equivalent weight 182 eq/g; trade name: Resinova ; Viscosity: 9000- 12000cps. The Mg-Al based Layered Double Hydroxides and Sodium dodecyl sulfate was obtain from Alderich Chemical Co.; Mum dai (India)

2.2 Preparation of the Layered Double Hydroxides Sodium Dodecyl Dulfate (LDH-SDS)

LDH was calcined in a muffle furnace at 440- 450⁰C for about 6 hr to alter it into metal oxide. The calcined product (LDH) 38 g was dispersed in a 120 ml of aqueous solution containing Sodium dodecyl sulfate (LDH-SDS) and the dispersion was stirred by magnetic stirrer for 24 hr at room temperature at 25⁰C. The regenerated SDS intercalated LDH (LDH-SDS) was filtered out followed by drying in oven at 100⁰C.

2.3 Preparation of Epoxy Nanocomposites:

For Preparation of the Epoxy Mg-Al LDH-SDS Nanocomposites system, the stoichiometric amount of Epoxy resin (27 g) was taken in beaker and then different % of LDH-SDS (1.0 to 5.0% with respective to epoxy resin) were added into beaker and mechanically stirred at room temperature for 1.5 hrs at 300 rpm and mixed thoroughly. Subsequently after through mixing of epoxy resin and LDH- SDS a stoichiometric amount of the curing agent (9 g) was added in each system and then again mechanically stirred at room temperature for 15 min at 300 rpm. After through mixing of epoxy resin-LDH-SDS and curing agent the viscous mixture was obtained, which were poured into flat aluminium foil mould and cured at room temperature for 24 hrs. Then sample plaque of cured product with different % LDH-SDS content were obtained and will keep as such for further characterization.

Figure 1. Schematic representation for preparation of epoxy nanocomposites.

Table No. 1 Preparation of (epoxy/SDS-LDH) nanocomposites.

Sample Code	Epoxy resin (g)	Curing Reagent(g)	Mg-Al SDS LDH (g)
SAP-0	27	9	-
SAP-1	27	9	0.27
SAP-2	27	9	0.54
SAP-3	27	9	0.83
SAP-4	27	9	1.08
SAP-5	27	9	1.35

III. Characterization of Nano Composites

3.1 X-ray diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern was recorded on a Shimadzu SD-D1 diffractometer with Cu target ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). The d spacing of the epoxy nanocomposites was analyzed by using Bragg's equation ($n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta$).

3.2 Mechanical Properties

Determination of Tensile Strength, Elongation-at- break and elastic modulus:

The Dumb-bell shaped samples were prepared and was used for the determination of the tensile strength, elongation-at-break and elastic modulus. The samples were prepared in a self designed teflon mould as per ASTM D638 standardization.

3.3 Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out using a Shimadzu Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TGA-50, Japan), in the temperature range between room temperature and 800⁰C at a heating rate of 10⁰C per min in nitrogen atmosphere with a flow rate of 50 mL/min. TG traces were obtained by plotting per cent residual weight against temperature.

3.4 Morphological Properties

The Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images of the fractured surface of samples were obtained by using high resolution and low vacuum SEM equipment (M/s FEI Company, USA; model: Quanta 200 FEG) to examine the microstructure and fractured surfaces of nano-composites. The samples were mounted on aluminium stubs using carbon tape. The samples were coated with a thin layer of platinum to prevent charging before the observation by SEM.

IV. Results and Discussions

4.1 X-ray diffraction (XRD)

XRD is a powerful technique for detect the exfoliation of SDS-LDH structures. **Fig. 2** shows the XRD patterns of the SDS-LDH /epoxy composites for distinct SDS-LDH content and dispersion agent [15].

Figure 2: X-ray diffraction patterns of various epoxy nanocomposites

Characteristic maxima of SDS-LDH ($2\theta = 32^\circ$ and 37°) are present in XRD spectra of all epoxy/SDS-LDH systems indicating successful incorporation of SDS-LDH into polymer matrix (Fig. 2). On the other hand, the disappearance of maxima at 7° , 11° , 20° and 23° , which originate from the layered structure of the filler, indicate intercalation and possibly exfoliation of SDS-LDH to form the epoxy nanocomposites.

4.2 Studies on Mechanical Properties

The results of tensile strength and elongation-at-break are summarized in the **Table 2** it is evidence from the results that the increase in loading of SDS-LDHs in epoxy matrix increased both the tensile strength and elongation-at-break.

Table 2: Experimental data sheet for mechanical properties of nano-composites

Sr. No	Sample Code	Tensile Strength in Kg/cm ²	Elongation at break (%)
1	SAP-0	75.91	0.97
2	SAP-1	78.52	1.27
3	SAP-2	84.36	1.46
4	SAP-3	89.82	1.67
5	SAP-4	90.94	1.99
6	SAP-5	95.21	2.37

Figure 3[a-b]: Variation of tensile strength and elongation-at-break with percentage loading of SDS-LDHs in epoxy matrix.

The values of tensile strength and elongation-at-break was found to be greatest in 5 wt% (SAP-5) SDS-LDHs loaded nanocomposite sample. The enhance of tensile strength and elongation-at-break might be due to the filling of SDS-LDHs into the amorphous region of matrix via uniform scattering up to 5 wt% (SAP-5)[16,17]. When the amorphous region of epoxy polymer matrix had been completely filled by the nano particles, the sample achieved highest tensile strength due to the load shearing by SDS-LDHs. The nanocomposite samples also showed the toughening behavior on addition of nano-filler for same composition, which led to enhance the elongation-at-break values.

4.3. Thermal stability.

The thermal stabilities of the Epoxy/SDS-LDH nanocomposites were studied by means of TGA. The TGA thermograms for the virgin epoxy resin and Epoxy/SDS LDH nanocomposites are shown in **Fig 4**:

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425

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Figure 4: TGA thermograms of Epoxy/SDS-LDH nanocomposites as a function of SDS-LDH content.

The thermal stability of the nanocomposites was significantly enhanced by the addition of SDS-LDH. In the virgin epoxy system, the degradation started at around 290°C. When SDS-LDH was added to the epoxy matrix, the IDT of the nanocomposites was at least 20°C higher than that of the virgin epoxy system. The T_{max} of the virgin epoxy system was 370°C, whereas upon addition of SDS-LDH into the epoxy matrix, the T_{max} of the nanocomposites appeared within the range of 400-410°C. These results can be interpreted with reference to the addition of SDS-LDH to the epoxy polymeric matrix system[18,19], which increased the surface contact area between the SDS-LDH particles and the epoxy matrix, which in turn prevented the heat diffusion during decomposition of the Epoxy/SDS LDH nanocomposites. The results can be attributed also to the increased cross-linking density of the nanocomposites. The char content for the nanocomposites at 800°C also was increased with the addition of SDS-LDH. A similar observation was reported by Chen *et al.* using rigid poly(vinyl chloride)/calcium carbonate nanocomposites.

4.4 Morphological Studies

Figure 5: SEM image of samples SAP-0, EPC-1, SAP-3, and SAP-5 respectively.

Surface morphology of epoxy/SDS-LDHs nanocomposites was further studied by the SEM analysis (Figure 5). With smaller magnification (Figure 3a) it can be seen that SDS-LDHs is consistently dispersed within the epoxy matrix. Larger magnification confirms intercalation of epoxy matrix within layered structure of LDH-B, but no complete exfoliation in any of the nanocomposites[20,21]. Only nanocomposite with 5 % of nanofiller shows partial exfoliation.

V. Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn:-

- 1) As the concentration of Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate double hydroxide (Mg-Al SDS-LDHs) increased in the nanocomposite samples, the tensile strength, elongation-at-break, increased and found maximum in SAP-5 sample. The enhancement in the mechanical

properties of nanocomposite samples were because load sharing by nano-particles, when subjected under load.

- 2) The high degree of intercalation of nano-particles was observed in SAP-5 sample than other nanocomposites, which showed the higher roughness and surface area to divert the crack initiation and propagation.
- 3) As the concentration of Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate Layered double hydroxides (Mg-Al SDS-LDHs) increased into the nanocomposite samples, the thermal properties also increase and found maximum in SAP-5 sample. The enhancement in the thermal properties of nanocomposite samples thus increasing the surface contact area between the SDS-LDHs particles and the epoxy matrix.

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